

Lambda Project

3RD SEMESTER

Istvan Marki, Casper Gouldbech Nielsen, Toke Frostholt Rasmussen

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1. INTRODUCTION

The principal objective of this semester project is to fully comprehend and apply the Agile Software Development Methodology which we have been learning throughout the most recent semester.

Last year we applied the Unified Process framework. The given time was almost the whole semester to finish our project. But this time we desperately need a way by which we can deliver a high quality, cost effective solution in *rapid time*.

The following report together with our final software product demonstrate that we have acquired enough experience and understanding of the agile method of software development. To reach this goal successfully, we have settled on creating a distributed service (a solution) that consists of a fake local sensor, a SOAP Web Service, a PHP Web Application and the Twitter API. The basic idea is to gather local weather information from a sensor and broadcast it. We will collect these measurements at a Proxy that resides on the same network and call our SOAP Service to store the sensor information in the database. The very same entity will Tweet the information using the Twitter API. Our PHP Web Application can connect to the API (both Twitter and SOAP) and retrieve the relevant data to display into the user's browser. The final product will be very simple because our focus will be on understanding the Scrum framework and using the agile methodologies properly.

To accomplish all of the above within the given 3 weeks' period of time, we trust in Agile due to its biggest promise: it is not only a software development methodology, but a way of working to deliver business value- faster, better and cheaper.

By cheaper and cost effective we mean relatively low resource usage.

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION

According to the 3rd semester project charter (El Allali, 2016), we ought to implement a very simple distributed service system. We've been given full independence regarding the system we are about to build. There won't be any '*real*' customer whose proposal or idea we must accept.

This time we use one of our fellow classmates' team, who are going to serve as a customer for us. We really look forward to it, due to our last semester's negative experience: *the overall lack of the presence of*

our client. This time, our *client team* will be present and available upon our request, basically any time needed.

This comes very handy, since we are going to implement the Agile Development Methodology.

Last year we were following the Unified Process, and our development lifecycle took up almost the whole semester. Now we are required to finish the whole process within 3 weeks of time. It comes with a quite different pace. Compared to the Unified Process' long 2-3 weeks of phases are going to be replaced with faster, shorter and rapid sprints.

Summarizing our expectations, we are not afraid of implementing the system itself, since we are regularly being checked by this semester's mock exams, and we are delightful with our grades and evaluation. What we are more concerned about, and this will be our main focus so as our *problem definition*:

“How do we implement the Agile mindset and Scrum framework to be the driving factor in our software development process?”

2.1. SUB PROBLEM

“Is it possible to implement Scrum in a group consisting of only three members?”

At the end of our report we will reflect to our problem definitions, and draw a conclusion according to our experience and first hand impressions.

3. COMPLY WITH AGILE PRACTICES

Summarizing the main arguments for our development process, we followed the professional advice and enforced the principles and guidelines behind the Agile Manifesto (Beck et al. 2001). Our main priority was to be adapting to change in general:

'Responding to change over following a plan'

During the 3rd semester a brand-new practice of evaluation and grading method has been introduced to us. We have trial exams (*mock exams*) so that the teachers can measure our performance against specific objectives. Consequently, we already have good experience in all the technical parts to be implemented. It is very helpful for us, since we will have time to focus on the methodology and the project management during development.

The Scrum Framework (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2016) is pictured by us (*See Figure 1.*) our project report skeleton (basically all sections and subsections) will deliberately follow this outline.

Figure 1

3.1. EXTREME PROGRAMMING (XP)

XP is a lightweight, efficient and flexible way of software development (Beck, 2005). In the following sections, we demonstrate which particular elements were combined and used by us.

3.1.1. SMALL RELEASES

During an Agile development process, it is paramount to deliver a working product quite often and early. This way we can get valuable feedback in time from our customer. Moreover, it is easier to test more frequently on smaller releases, so that we can avoid running into large and problematic failures. The reason of testing is to make our program fail. In case a full rebuild is needed from scratch, the time lost has not been that significant. Given the 3 weeks' time in which we need to deliver our project, this is a principal practice of our development.

3.1.2. PAIR PROGRAMMING

When there was a complicated task, an extra pair of eyes was great help for the developer. Also, one of the best way to learn is to teach and explain. For our mutual better understanding, we found the pair programming method extremely useful. We found out that the tasks took almost the half of the estimated time, when we sat together creating programmer-pairs.

3.1.3. CODING STANDARD & COLLECTIVE OWNERSHIP

How we code is our signature. We set up high standards which all of us needed to adhere to. Using best practices, conventions and recommendations by the Microsoft Developer Network (MSDN). The rules were clear and accepted by everyone. We even determined how to comment our commits when we were working with our coding repository. By setting up these standards which all of us need to adhere to, we can rely on each other. Having said that we encourage everyone to contribute to all segments of the project. (See *Project Proposal 4.1*)

3.1.4. PLANNING GAME

- *Sorting the user stories by business value (by the client)*

When we had the first meeting with our client team, we played the planning poker game. We presented our four User Stories, explaining in detail our ideas and the available features, then they voted on each stories by placing their cards on them.

- *Sorting the tasks by risk (by the developers)*

When we were planning our velocity, we sat together (the developers only) and placed the cards with different values. First we voted on the lowest and then up till the highest task. It was very exciting, how we can argue, and convince each other.

The result is a prioritized list in both of the cases above. The Planning Game was a great team building tool as well. It taught us how to overcome disagreements! We had an open discussion with awesome arguments. After carefully listening to each other we got to a better understanding of the whole project.

3.1.5. TEST DRIVEN DEVELOPMENT

As we described in our checklist (*See section 4.2 Definition of Done*) we enforce a rule that no code shall be left without being tested. A good practice is to write Unit Tests and test cases before a single line of code is written. When a developer finishes a task, it is not *'done'* yet. Even if it is working properly! We set up rules that no one can work in the master branch, nor the developer branch of our code repository. Even before the smallest change, a developer should make his own branch, and work on it independently. Only when particular tests passed and double checked for bugs and every change are peer reviewed, subsequently the branch can be merged to the original one.

3.1.6. SIMPLE DESIGN

Compared to the recent years' assignments and semester projects, this project is developed on a much tighter time schedule. The focus is on the project management and not on the development. Enough design is implemented to meet the current requirements and no more. This has proved to be the most difficult during the project. We had to keep reminding each other not to dive deeper into details, however hard it was. We selected some of the principles of XP, the acronyms like: Do The Simplest Thing That Could Possibly Work (DTSTTCPW) Keep It Simple, Stupid! (KISS) You Aren't Going to Need It! (YAGNI). These principles reminded us always to work on the story we have, not something we think we're going to need. This helped us stay focused and not get carried away.

3.1.7. SUSTAINABLE PACE

We agreed at the project proposal which days we would meet on. We selected Mondays-Wednesdays-Fridays independently from our school's schedule. By this agreement we had enough time left for doing our part-time jobs, and the weekends for our family and spare time activities. By inserting these gap days between our *'active'* project days, we could always have a fresh start at each time.

3.2. SCRUM TOOLS

In the following section, we describe the tools used to make our Scrum process easier to manage. Using Agile methods and Scrum practices are only useful if you have tools to support those methods, it does not matter if those tools are pen and paper, whiteboard, a digital media or all three. To support the Agile and Scrum methods we have searched for the tools that would suit best our need and have looked over different approaches to the same problem – finding the right tool for the right job.

3.3. TEAM SERVICES

We settled on using Team Services as our project management tool. Team Services is a project management tool, planning tool, build tool and a version control tool – basically it is a tool for the entire process from idea to deployment. Team Services is free for up to 5 members per Team which was fine for us since we were only 3. Team Services integrate very well with Visual Studio and Git for version control – and have extensions for a variety of other tools for building, deploying and maintaining software. Here is an overview of the features we used most frequently:

3.3.1. TEAM VELOCITY (CAPACITY)

Figure 2

The above picture (See Figure 2.) shows the Capacity page where the manager can set team day off, individual day off, which activities each team member participates in as well as the capacity per day of that given activity.

On the right-hand side, the green bars below each member as well as the average capacity for the entire team for the given sprint is shown. Imagine we had too much work in this sprint (Sprint 3 as highlighted on the left-hand side), then the bar would be red – as the given team member would not have time enough to complete the tasks assigned to him.

3.3.2. BACKLOG

Figure 3

The above picture (See Figure 3.) shows the backlog of Sprint 3. As this was our first attempt at using Team Services we obviously made some mistakes. Here you can see that every item created in the backlog is actually a User Story – where most of them aren't. Most are features, testing or documentation, which should have been created as unparented tasks rather than a User Story. Each user story then has tasks assigned to them where we give the time estimate for how long time it takes to finish each task.

3.3.4. BURNDOWN CHART

Burndown for: Sprint 2

Figure 5

The Burndown chart (See Figure 5.) is a tool to see if you are ahead or behind on schedule. From the Burndown chart example above you can see we have followed the ideal trend all the way to the 30th. The reason that the 30th is behind schedule is because the day is not done yet, and as such, we still have tasks that needs to be closed before the day is over.

3.3.5. CODE REPOSITORY

Files overview (See Figure 6.):

Figure 6

Branch overview (See Figure 7.):

Figure 7

The two above pictures show the overview of the code repository features that we used. We created the repository (repo) and cloned this repo into Visual Studio. Now, every time we commit, push, pull or fetch it will be to and from this repo.

3.3.6. SCRUM MEETINGS (DAILY STANDUP)

We use a predefined formula to log our meetings. This contains the specific date, the duration of the meeting in minutes, the participants with their roles and the agenda. The daily standup Scrum meetings gave an opportunity to get a clear picture of what the other people on the team are currently working on, and what the status of the project is, and get help if anything is blocking their progress (Green, 2016).

In every meeting we asked ourselves the following questions:

- *What have you done since the last stand up?*
- *What do you plan to do until the next stand up?*
- *Is there anything blocking your progress?*

4. SPRINT ZERO

Sprint Zero served as a discovery and agreement phase for our project, but like with any other sprint, the purpose was to deliver value. In this sprint, we settled on the team and then divided the team roles for the duration of the development. Because our team only exist of three members, we decided that each member should have the experience of taking the part of Scrum Master, Product Owner and Development Team in one Sprint each (See Table 1 in section 4.1.5).

After we had agreed on the team and our individual roles, we set about finding a project idea that we would develop. This did not have to be a huge elaborate project, but just complicated enough to require us to use the different technologies and techniques we have acquired through this semester. We decided to create a simple platform where anglers can see the current readings of a sensor located near the shore and from this information decide whether it is better fishing conditions in Denmark or Sweden.

In this Sprint, we also wrote our project proposal including Shared Vision and a team contract, which served as common guideline for the project. To keep a consistent workflow, we also created a Definition of Done.

4.1. PROJECT PROPOSAL

4.1.1. OUR PERSONAL VISION FOR THE PROJECT

We wish to *increase* our knowledge within the Agile mindset and the Scrum methodology.

We want to *experience* a true Agile team using the Scrum methodology to create a distributed system.

We would like to compare the Unified Process (UP) with the Agile practices and Scrum methodology.

4.1.2. TEAM CONTRACT

We established a team contract which every team member needs to adhere to. The rules are strict, and by not obeying nor following them has a serious and immediate consequence: dismissal from the team.

- Agreed meeting time: Monday-Wednesday-Friday from 08:00 to 15:00
- In case of sickness, the team member is expected to notify the rest no later than 2 hours before the meeting
- All members are expected to respect each other's idea as well as opinions
- All members must adhere to deadlines established by the school
- All members are expected to write clean code with comments, and test everything before pushing to the repository

4.1.3. RISK MANAGEMENT

- *Surprises*
In case of the sickness of a group member the solution is to redistribute and reassign the tasks
- *Loss of data*

Using GIT repository and version control, and back-up files in the cloud services

- *Loss of motivation*

Try out new tools, deliberately aiming high to find challenges. Scrum is about people, a new approach of product development. We will enforce ourselves to use the rituals and artifacts and roles of Scrum to get the work done more efficiently and effectively.

4.1.4. SHARED VISION

'Fisherman's Friend' aspires to equip its users with a powerful service. We not only provide our anglers with the latest weather reading, but we keep them safe as well. What we came up with, is highly unlikely a product at all. We define and describe it more like a service. There is not any standalone program itself, that the user needs to download and install. Almost everything we have built and coded, is invisible, located under the hood.

INTRODUCTION

- Our workload is dedicated to serve the people who lack information to organize their free time activities, so as their hobbies.
- We are mimicking a professional remote weather station located by the coastal shores of North-East Sjælland, which is monitoring several conditions by a sensor connected to the internet.
- Our service will help anglers decide whether to go fishing in Denmark or in Sweden
- Our system will notify them if any extreme weather conditions are developing

POSITIONING

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem of	<i>Shifting weather conditions</i>
affects	<i>Coastal people (living seaside)</i>
impacting	<i>Their safety and revenue</i>
a successful solution	<i>To create a system which is monitoring the weather conditions and provides systematic observations.</i>

PRODUCT POSITION STATEMENT

For	<i>Coastal people</i>
Who	<i>Need reliable, detailed weather service</i>
The (service name)	<i>Fisherman's Friend</i>
That	<i>Provides up-to-date and corresponding info</i>
Unlike	<i>Conventional media services: TV/Newspaper forecast</i>
Our product	<i>Exclusively focuses on fishing, as a coastal lifestyle activity.</i>

STAKEHOLDER SUMMARY

Name	Description	Responsibilities
Developer Team	<i>The owners of this project</i>	<i>Confront and fully comply with Agile practices</i>
Coastal People	<i>Subscribed to our Twitter feed/visiting our website</i>	<i>Secure themselves by gathering information regarding their working conditions.</i>

USER ENVIRONMENT

Coastal living people must be aware of current weather threats before they sail out. If any danger is about to escalate they will be notified.

Our fully functional solution at work would be described as follows:

- A built in meteorological logic is coded into our application, which is written by experts
- The logic is evaluating the data, and determines the upcoming weather forecast.
- By providing relevant information via our Website, the anglers can choose between their fishing destination of Denmark or Sweden
- In case of any dangerous upcoming whether condition, they will be notified at once.
- By storing the readings in the cloud, we contribute to an open sourced big data storage, which can be analyzed later on by climate experts.

We dismissed the rest of the *vision template document* given to us, simply because they did not add any value to our project. More precisely it reminded us very much of a Business Analytic Artifact, which are recommended to be used in the Unified Process.

4.1.5. TEAM ROLES IN OUR PROJECT

As our group only consisted of three team members we were enough people to fill the Scrum roles, but not enough to have a development team consisting of the recommended 4-8 engineers (Green, 2016). Fortunately, we did not find this a problem as we were aware before the projected started that each member would be taking part in every part of the project.

To make sure that each member of our group had the opportunity to experience what it's like to have the different Scrum roles we swapped according to the table shown below (*See Table 1*).

	Sprint 1	Sprint 2	Sprint 3
Product Owner	Istvan	Toke	Casper
Scrum Master	Casper	Istvan	Toke
Developer	Toke	Casper	Istvan

Table 1

4.2. DEFINITION OF DONE

The Definition of Done is a Scrum artefact consisting of a checklist of activities and artefacts that the team has agreed is required for something to be considered as completed (Agile Academy, 2011). They are made to make sure that any delivered feature is in fact truly done. To get a clear DoD we sat down together and discussed what we had to do in order to make a task ready for delivery. The following checklist is our final DoD:

- Code is finished
- Solution builds without errors
- Relevant classes, methods and code blocks are commented
- The changes have been thoroughly tested and pair reviewed
- Working code is pushed to remote repository
- Documentation is updated

4.3. TESTING

Here we will describe the following three main testing methods we have used in the project. We will explain in detail how we implemented each type of testing in the Sprint Retrospective.

We have chosen to revert the order a little bit to fit our needs better. We have done the following:

1. System testing
2. Integration testing
3. User acceptance testing (UAT)

4.3.1. SYSTEM

System testing falls within the scope of black-box testing. The tester is not required to have any knowledge about the inner design, the logic nor the code. However, we have used it as a white-box testing method to test the system requirements and functional requirements from the developer's perspective.

The general idea behind system testing is to test the functional requirements specification(s) (FRS) and/or system requirements specification(s) (SRS). The idea is to test the system's performance according to the above requirements – does the system fulfill the requirements there is to the system?

We have used the system testing, to test if the system works as intended. Fx. Can we connect to the database and save and/or retrieve data?

4.3.2. INTEGRATION

Integration testing falls within the scope of both black-box and white-box testing. The idea behind integration testing is to take the system and put it together as one unit and then, test the integration between these systems.

We have modified integration testing a bit, to fit our need better. We have put it after the system testing and modified it to include the integration between our sub systems as well as 3rd party systems.

Fx. How does the integration between the Proxy and the SOAP Service work?

4.3.3. USER ACCEPTANCE TEST (UAT)

The User Acceptance Test is white-box testing. It is where the system is tested to see if it fits the user's needs.

In our project, the UAT was conducted by the client. According to the user acceptance criteria (also written by the client). The client then accepts or declines the delivery. If a delivery is declined it will go back to development to fix the errors and then raised throughout the different levels of testing once more:

1. System testing
2. Integration testing
3. User Acceptance testing

4.4. WRITING USER STORIES

After agreeing on the project and forming our Shared Vision, the next step was to create User Stories. We had agreed that besides our shared common vision the goal of this sprint was to deliver a Product Backlog. A Product Backlog is by made writing User Stories and prioritizing these into a list of features

that the system must consist of. Unfortunately, our first take on writing User Stories was not very successful, as we had misunderstood the concept about writing User Stories. User Stories have to add a specific value to the client/customer. As seen in User Story 2 and 3 below this is not the case. See section 5.5 (*Sprint Retrospective – deciding to end the Sprint early*) for refinements of the User Stories.

USER STORY 1: AS A PRODUCT OWNER I WANT TO BE ABLE TO DISPLAY THE CURRENT DANISH WEATHER SO THE USERS WILL BE TO DECIDE IF THE CONDITIONS ARE GOOD TO GO FISHING

- Task 1: Create a fake UDP broadcast console application, mimicking a remote professional weather stationary with sensors.
- Task 2: Create a UDP listener (Proxy) to read our fake weather station's live measurements
- Task 3: Create a REST API
- Task 4: Consume the REST API with a console application

USER STORY 2: AS A PRODUCT OWNER I WANT TO BE ABLE TO STORE WEATHER CONDITIONS

- Task 1: Create a Server and a Database in the cloud
- Task 2: Store sensor data in the Database by a console application

USER STORY 3: AS A PRODUCT OWNER I WANT TO BE ABLE TO RETRIEVE WEATHER CONDITIONS

- Task 1: Retrieve sensor data from Database by a console application

USER STORY 4: AS A USER I WANT TO BE ABLE TO COMPARE THE DANISH AND THE SWEDISH WEATHER CONDITIONS FOR FISHING

- Task 1: Set up the PHP Web Application in the cloud
 - Task 2: Set up the Twitter API authentication
 - Task 3: Set up the PHP to consume data from Database
 - Task 4: Set up the PHP to send queries towards Twitter API
-

4.4.1. PRELIMINARY PRODUCT BACKLOG

The User Stories above created the following Product Backlog, which we used Planning Poker to estimate.

- As a product owner I want to be able to display the current Danish weather so the users will be to decide if the conditions are good to go fishing
- As a Product Owner I want to be able to store weather conditions
- As a product owner I want to be able to retrieve weather conditions
- As a user I want to be able to compare the Danish and the Swedish weather conditions for fishing

Note that these were later changed and are just displayed here to show how our project evolved and adjusted as we reflected on our work.

4.5. OVERALL PLANNING

With this project, we wanted to experience what it is like using the Scrum framework as a project management tool. Sprints are fixed length and will normally last 2-4 weeks (Sommerville 2011), but as we only had three weeks for this project we decided to have shorter Sprints of 1 week each. This gave us the opportunity to work with Sprints according to the guidelines and also gave each team member the opportunity to act as the different team roles used in Scrum.

The diagram below (See Figure 8.) illustrates the overall timeline of our project indicating where the individual Sprints begin and end.

Figure 8

4.6. SPRINT 1 PLANNING

The entire team participated in the planning of Sprint 1. We decided that the primary goal of Sprint 1 was to have a database and a fake sensor broadcasting data. We discussed the User Stories and created detailed tasks which were added to the Sprint Backlog. Then the Sprint Backlog included only the tasks which could be completed within the available hours. The Sprint Backlog for Sprint 1 is described in Section 5.1 (*Sprint Backlog*)

4.7. PLANNING POKER

Planning Poker is a technique used in XP to estimate the relative workload of each User Story. The purpose of it is to make sure that everyone makes an independent estimation, which is not influenced by what other people in the game have already said. Therefore, we took our User Stories with the corresponding Acceptance Tests to another group and agreed that on each User Story every participant have to place one card face down. The Product Owner briefly explained the different User Stories and we went through the User Stories one by one turning over the cards when all participants had placed his card on the User Stories. The values displayed by the cards made up the Story Points for each User Story.

5. SPRINT 1

Sprint 1 was the period that got us on track. Here we got a real understanding of Scrum and how to properly implement it, all the way from meeting with the client (requirements and feedback), writing correct User Stories and the Sprint Planning, Planning Poker and estimation. More detailed explanation will be described in the following sections below.

5.1. SPRINT BACKLOG

The following picture (*See Figure 9.*) shows the entire Sprint Backlog, including documentation, testing and meetings.

3rd semester project Team Sprint 1

Backlog **Board** Capacity

New

Figure 9

This Sprint Backlog shows many signs that we at this point have

1. Misused the Scrum tool. Notice that all tasks are added as a User Story.
2. Misunderstood Scrum.

We should have taken in the top priority tasks in the top priority User Story and worked on that. More on this will follow in the Sprint Review (*See Section 5.6*).

5.2. SCRUM MEETING

In this paragraph (See section 6.2 and 7.2 as well) we deliver the internal logs we kept of our daily standup Scrum Meetings. They will display only briefly the date, the duration, the roles and the respective day's agenda.

As you can see, in the beginning they almost took 20-30 minutes of time, as we did not have much experience just yet.

5.2.1. MONDAY

21st November, 2016 (duration 30 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Casper (Scrum Master), Istvan (Product Owner), Toke (Developer)

Agenda:

- Domain Model
- Scrum diary Documentation will be done in MS OneNote 2016
- MS Azure: setting up Resource Group, Database and the Server
- Testing Database via Console Application
- Fake UDP Sensor documentation, draw a class diagram
- Question: will the data broadcasting be a local one? Yes, due to school's network security restrictions
- Establish Team Contract
- New tool and interface: MS Team Services for Project Management

5.2.2. WEDNESDAY

23rd November, 2016 (duration: 30 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Casper (Scrum Master), Istvan (Product Owner), Toke (Developer)

Agenda:

- Summarizing our Scrum Board by the Scrum Master (we have enough data for visualization)
- Remaining tasks for the current Sprint
- Burndown chart, Tools used during the Sprint
- Scrum methodology itself, research needed
- Shared Vision, Problem Definition, Report outline

5.2.3. FRIDAY

25th November, 2016 (duration 20 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Casper (Scrum Master), Istvan (Product Owner), Toke (Developer)

Agenda:

- Needful to do's: finish the allocated documentation, plan Sprint 2

5.3. BURNDOWN CHART

In the picture below (See Figure 10.) is a representation of Sprint 1 Burndown chart:

Burndown for: Sprint 1

Figure 10

As seen, the first struggle we had was to get the tool to display the data correctly. We found that starting the Sprint (within the tool) one day before it would display the data correctly. As the green line shows (our available capacity), we divided up the Sprint for quite little and lightweight tasks.

The Story Points estimation was correct. The first day we delivered 25 Story Points where it was estimated that we could deliver a total of 24 amongst the entire team.

5.4. DONE

We managed to deliver all the tasks projected in this Sprint. Including:

- Setting up the database and hosting on Azure Cloud. Together with the documentation of it.
- Setting up a test application to write into the database. As well as diagramming and documentation.
- Setting up a test application to read from the database. Together with diagramming and documentation.
- We diagrammed the Domain Model (*See Appendix 1*) which has been discarded afterwards as we found it adding no value to the project at all.
- We diagrammed the Core Architecture (*See Appendix 2*) and documented it.
- We documented the Sprint, the code, and all the initial start of the project report.
- We stopped the Sprint early (*See section 5.5*) and held a Retrospective followed by a Review and then planning for Sprint 2.

5.5. SPRINT RETROSPECTIVE – DECIDING TO END THE SPRINT EARLY

FRIDAY

25th November, 2016 (duration 60 minutes)

When we met up Friday morning we held a Scrum meeting where we agreed (based on new information from colleagues and books) to stop the Sprint now and use the rest of the day to redo the User Stories, Planning Poker and setting up for Sprint 2.

When we wrote the first User Stories we made the mistake of putting ourselves prior to the client. This meant that the User Stories did not add value to the client as they are supposed to.

- *Why have our previous User Stories failed?*

First of all, a User Story should capture a complete slice of functionality (Green, 2016). Moreover, every User Story should add value to the product. At last it should follow the simple formula: *As a ..., I want to..., so that ...*

Let's examine the User Story "*As a Product Owner I want to be able to retrieve weather conditions*"

- It completely lacks the explanation '*so that...*', we are missing the purpose, consequently the desired state which would have added the value to it. Why is this valuable to us or the client?

NEW USER STORY (EPIC USER STORY)

During the meeting we made a decision, and agreed on one User Story only. This User Story was then broken into subtasks by the development team. The purpose was very simple: If we have one User Story, the client will write the Acceptance Test on the back of the card. This means we can have them testing only the system as a whole.

But that would remind us to Waterfall development. In order to keep our process Agile, we wrote Integration Tests (I&T) and Component Interface Tests (CIT). In I&T we can verify the interfaces between components (MSDN 2016a, 2016b) and by CIT we can check the handling of data passed between units or subsystem components.

At the end of each Sprint we meet up with our client and involved them into the testing process above. By this practice our development stays Agile, since we still get feedback which is the most valuable in our case. However, they are mostly technical tests, we still can change components which will deeply effect the whole outcome and final state of our product.

As a user I want to be able to compare the current Danish and Swedish coastal weather so that I can decide where to go fishing.

- Task 1: Create fake UDP broadcast console app
- Task 2: Create a Listener (Proxy) to read the UDP broadcast
- Task 3: Create a SOAP Web Service
- Task 4: Consume the SOAP Service with a console application
- Task 5: Create a Database in the cloud
- Task 6: Store sensor data in the Database by a console application
- Task 7: Retrieve data from Database by a console application

- Task 8: Set up the PHP Web Application
- Task 9: Set up the Twitter API
- Task 10: Set up the PHP to consume data from Database
- Task 11: Set up the PHP to send queries towards Twitter

VOTE	TASK Number	Task details	Weight	Estimated time	+ 1 hour each task for technical testing
1 st	Task 5	Create DB	0	1 hour	
2 nd	Task 1	Fake UDP	½	1 hour	
3 rd	Task 6	Store data to DB	1	1 hour	
4 th	Task 7	Read data from DB	2	1 hour	
5 th	Task 4	Test SOAP by VCF	3	0.75 hour	
6 th	Task 2	Proxy	5	2 hours	
7 th	Task 3	Create SOAP	8	4 hours	
8 th	Task 8	PHP Web App	13	6 hours	
9 th	Task 10	PHP consume DB	20	10 hours	
10 th	Task 9	Twitter API	40	20 hours	
11 th	Task 11	PHP queries to Twitter	100	20 hours	

The Acceptance criteria for our User Story are as follows:

- Up-to-date tweets about Swedish weather is displayed
- Up-to-date tweets about Danish weather is displayed

We then proceeded to play the Planning Poker (still only the developers) (*See Figure 11.*) to estimate the difficulty of the tasks and afterwards estimate the Story Points we considered it would take to complete the task. In the following pictures of us playing planning poker on the tasks (*See Figure 11.*), given that we only had one User Story:

Figure 11

5.6. SPRINT REVIEW

FRIDAY, CLIENT MEETING

25th November, 2016 (duration 15 minutes)

We held an *informal meeting* with our client at the first time with our deliverables. We intentionally kept it very informal, as suggested by Mike Cohn (MGS, 2016).

If we had more than one User Story, than we could have called it Acceptance Test (UAT). Since we only have one Epic User Story we keep the UAT to the end of the 3rd Sprint. Despite of the technical nature of our demonstration we still found it useful to show our current progress to our client.

- We demonstrated how we could save and afterwards retrieve the saved data in the database hosted on Azure.

We could have offered some different options to the client. If we had bigger data entities, then for example we could show what different pricing tiers come with significant speed differences using Azure Cloud Services etc. Moreover, we could get updates if any of their requirements changed.

The client was satisfied with the result of the sprint as it was clear that we could both store and receive data from the database on the Azure cloud. We moved all the tasks involved in Done into Closed. We could not move the items into Done-Done as we had no Acceptance Test for these items.

5.7. SPRINT 2 PLANNING

FRIDAY

25th November, 2016 (duration 60 minutes)

From Sprint 1, we had established an estimate of around 72 Story Points ((8 hours * 3 people) * 3 days) and proved that we could deliver around 25 Story Points per day so we settled on setting up our velocity a bit higher.

We stated that each member could now deliver 9.2 Story Points per day which sums up to 82,8 Story Points for the entire Sprint. We also settled that we would work on our own to complete these tasks. This adds up to a total velocity of 110 Story Points for the sprint.

We took the User Story and added all the tasks to the Sprint until we could either see that

1. The bar showing available velocity was full.
2. There were no tasks left.

It came to the latter. Which meant that we added a "Development buffer" of 18 points/hours.

We also allocated a lot of hours to documentation (which includes all report writing, documentation of code etc.). This added up to a total of 31,5 Story Points. We added a 10 Story Points documentation buffer to be able to use that if we made wrong estimation and changes arose.

6. SPRINT 2

In the 2nd Sprint we experienced something at first hand. A team member got sick. We responded swiftly to the change by reassigning the tasks and kept him up to date with our progress during the working hours. At the end, we successfully managed to keep on track with our original plan.

During the development process we used Pair Programming as a useful practice from the Extreme Programming tool.

6.1. SPRINT BACKLOG

The Sprint Backlog (See *Figure 12.*) is our to-do list for the respective week. It was created by the whole team, and maintained by the Scrum Master daily.

Item	Status	Assignee
+ As a user I want to be able to view data about the weathe... *** ● Active	Active	Casper Guldb...
■ Create a proxy to collect UDP broadcast	● Closed	Toke Frosthol...
■ Create SOAP service	● Closed	Istvan Marki
■ Consume the SOAP service	● Closed	Toke Frosthol...
■ Create the PHP web application	● Closed	Casper Guldb...
■ Consume data from the Database by the PHP web applicat...	● Closed	Casper Guldb...

Figure 12

6.2. SCRUM MEETING

6.2.1. MONDAY

28th November, 2016 (duration: 15 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Istvan (Scrum Master), Toke (Product Owner), Casper (Developer)

Agenda:

- PHP Web Application, hosted in Azure
- Create SOAP Service, hosted in Azure

6.2.2. WEDNESDAY

30th November, 2016 (duration 15 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Istvan (Scrum Master), Toke (Product Owner), Casper (Developer)

Agenda:

- Documentation of the code: UDP, Proxy, SOAP, PHP

6.2.3. FRIDAY

2nd December, 2016 (duration 15 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Istvan (Scrum Master), Toke (Product Owner), Casper (Developer)

Agenda:

- Rest of the documentation: Sprint Zero, 1 and 2

6.3. BURNDOWN CHART

Burndown for: Sprint 2

Figure 13

Due to unforeseen circumstances (see 28th and 30th November at the burndown chart) we had more remaining work as we have actually planned (See *Figure 13*). One team member was absent, but he recovered on Friday and we managed to finish all planned tasks with hard work.

6.4. DONE

In this Sprint we delivered all the tasks and nearly the entire User Story in time. We delivered:

- The UDP broadcaster
- The Proxy (to pick up UDP broadcast)
- The SOAP Service. And hosting in Azure
- The PHP Web Application. And hosting in Azure
- Make the PHP Web Application to consume the SOAP Service
- Documentation of the Sprint
- Documentation of Scrum
- Documentation of code

6.5. SPRINT RETROSPECTIVE

6.5.1. FRIDAY

2nd December, 2016 (duration 10 minutes)

The velocity for this Sprint was fairly high, yet we managed to finish on Friday and delivered the last tasks that was in the Sprint Backlog.

We estimate that we can proceed with this velocity, if not increase it slightly.

We have now delivered a fully working application that starts with a UDP broadcast, the transmitted data is being picked up by the Proxy, sent to the SOAP Service, stored in the database and retrieved by the PHP Web Application through the SOAP Service.

6.5.2. STARFISH RETROSPECTIVE

Figure 14

Because we had difficulties earlier in the process and because we wanted to get familiar with as many of the different Scrum tools, we used a tool, called Starfish Retrospectives (Kua, 2011) to visualize and identify ways to improve the next Sprint. (See Figure 14.)

- **Keep doing:** to regularly review the project report, daily updating TFS boards
- **More of:** taking screenshots from TFS boards and Backlogs, writing the documentation
- **Start doing:** Pair Programming, Git Kraken repository management tool
- **Stop doing:** drawing diagrams which doesn't add value
- **Less of:** explaining Scrum theories in the project report

We ran a brainstorming event with the team, so that we can reflect on a deeper degree of activities and practices. It helps us understand the practices without having them fit in the category '*good*' and '*not good*'.

6.6. SPRINT REVIEW

The Sprint Review was quite informal. The Product Owner discussed the Backlog, summarized what has been left for the last Sprint. We checked the Burndown chart, and double checked our estimations.

FRIDAY, CLIENT MEETING

2nd December, 2016 (duration 20 minutes)

Once again we held an informal meeting with the client. We demonstrated:

- The sensor broadcasting data
- The Proxy picking up the data and calling the SOAP Service to store the data
- The PHP Web App to retrieve data from the database

The client was satisfied with the result of the Sprint as it was clear that the broadcasting worked as expected and we were able to work with the database. Additionally, we demonstrated the simple website.

6.7. SPRINT 3 PLANNING

FRIDAY

2nd December, 2016 (duration 15 minutes)

We have settled on continuing the velocity from the previous Sprint (Sprint 2), which added up to a total of 110 Story Points. We found this velocity to be satisfactory to our capabilities.

We have 2 tasks remaining in our User Story. They were added to this Sprint as well as the documentation for the Sprint, finishing the report and the mandatory Scrum meetings, meeting with client (delivering the finished product) and the Retrospective.

Figure 15

As the Sprint Backlog (See Figure 15.) shows we have the capability to take in more tasks, however, currently there isn't any. This means we can adjust to changes if needed.

7. SPRINT 3

In Sprint 3 we felt comfortable on track after our adjustments due to the issues we experienced in Sprint 1. We completed our tasks on time and managed to have a successful Acceptance Test with client.

Once again we used Pair Programming because the PHP part of the project is unfamiliar to us and therefore required some extra attention while also giving every team member a chance to learn from it.

7.1. SPRINT BACKLOG

Figure 16. shows the Sprint Backlog for Sprint 3. It contains the only remaining features from the Product Backlog. We have estimated these two tasks to be quite complicated and we deliberately made sure to plan accordingly.

As a user I want to be able to view data about the weather so I ...	Active	Casper Guldb...	15
Use Twitter API to tweet sensor information	Closed	Toke Frosthol...	
Use Twitter API to query Tweets by the PHP web application	Active	Casper Guldb...	15

Figure 16

7.2. SCRUM MEETING

7.2.1. MONDAY

5th December, 2016 (duration: 15 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Toke (Scrum Master), Casper (Product Owner), Istvan (Developer)

Agenda:

- Tasks to do: Twitter API C# in Proxy, Twitter call in PHP, report documentation

7.2.2. WEDNESDAY

7th December, 2016 (duration: 15 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Toke (Scrum Master), Casper (Product Owner), Istvan (Developer)

Agenda:

- PHP
- Documentation of the report

7.2.3. FRIDAY

9th December, 2016 (duration: 5 minutes)

Scrum Roles:

- Toke (Scrum Master), Casper (Product Owner), Istvan (Developer)

Agenda:

- Finishing up report and the Sprint 3 documentation

7.3. BURNDOWN CHART

Figure 17. below displays the Burndown chart at the end of the final Sprint. We can see that we overestimated the task of implementing the functionality to use the Twitter API.

Burndown for: Sprint 3

Figure 17

7.4. DONE

All the features from the Sprint Backlog were successfully completed and ready for delivery. The first task on the list "Use Twitter API to tweet sensor data" was completed on Monday while the second task "Use Twitter API to query Tweets by the PHP Web Application" was more complicated, however they were both completed within the time estimation. This meant that we had the entire Friday to finish the report including proofreading etc.

7.5. SPRINT RETROSPECTIVE

7.5.1. FRIDAY

9th December, 2016 (duration 15 minutes)

Should the client accept the product and make it pass the Acceptance Criteria, this Retrospective concludes the end of Sprint 3 and the end of the project.

The continued velocity that we continued from Sprint 2, worked well in Sprint 3 (see Burndown chart for the Sprint as Figure 17.). We would estimate that we could continue this velocity, should the project be prolonged by another Sprint.

We have now delivered the full product; A UDP broadcaster, the Proxy that picks up the broadcast and Tweet the information as well as send it to the database though the SOAP Service. The PHP Web Application which can fetch the data from the database through the SOAP Service and display the Tweets done by the proxy as well as a Swedish fisherman.

7.6. SPRINT REVIEW

As in the previous Sprint our Sprint Review was quite informal. The Product Owner compared the Sprint Backlog with the delivered features. The client accepted the Acceptance Criteria for the User Story:

- Up-to-date tweets about Swedish weather is displayed
- Up-to-date tweets about Danish weather is displayed

Both criteria were accepted by the client and fulfilled their expectation of the product, based upon the User Story. The client was overall very satisfied with the supplied product.

We discussed the future of the product and the client wishes that the services are not maintained. The product is delivered as-is and the client is pleased with the result.

8. TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

In the following section, we explain briefly the nuts and bolts of our system. Step-by-step providing just enough details to supply the reader with the definite reasons why we committed ourselves to the selected applications.

8.1. NETWORK APPLICATION

A network application consists of a pair of programs: a client program and a server program (Kursoe 2013, p.182). When we execute the application, the server and the client start to communicate with each other using sockets.

8.1.1. UDP SENSOR BROADCASTER (CLIENT APP)

According to our 3rd semester project charter (El Allali, 2016) it is a mandatory task to use a Raspberry Pi. The Pi can serve as a standalone mini-computer, which is wire-connected to a sensor. In theory, this sensor can measure different weather conditions like: light, wind and temperature at a given time.

The usage of the Raspberry Pi, which we could borrow from the school, is very limited. We came up with the idea of mimicking the remote sensor by using the technic we acquired in the Computer Networks and Distributed Systems (CODS) lectures. So, that we developed a fake-sensor application which is broadcasting data (the fake measurements of the current weather).

The size of the data which is transferred by our sensor is quite small, and we would like to make the broadcasting service run non-stop continuously. To satisfy these conditions, we decided on a client program using UDP sockets due to its connectionless state and the small packet size of the sent data.

8.1.2. PROXY / UDP RECEIVER (SERVER APP)

In order to receive sensor data broadcasted by our fake sensor, a console application running on the same network as the broadcaster was necessary. It is a simple console application that listens on the same port as specified in broadcaster. Whenever it picks up a message from the broadcaster it will decode the array of bytes into a string allowing us to split the message and thereby getting the individual values for the temperature, light, wind and timestamp contained in the UDP datagram package. When all data has been split and converted into the desired format, the application saves it to our

database using our SOAP Service, before it once again starts listening for incoming transmission. Moreover, we implemented a logic into it: each reading is tweeted by our twitter account.

8.2. SOAP SERVICE

Our architecture is a distributed system (Kursoe 2013, p. 5). It involves multiple applications running on different end systems. The end systems can be located on independently running networked computers. The applications need to communicate with each other by passing messages.

A central 'controller' is needed, which defines how the applications pass the messages when communicating with each other. This controller is an API (Application Programming Interface). We deployed a Windows Communication Foundation (WCF) service-oriented application into the cloud which is going to serve as an API in our architecture. The WCF was an obvious choice for the job, because it can be used to communicate using different protocols and from different kinds of applications, moreover it is possible to test it even before we connect it to any applications.

Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP) defines a set of architectural principles by which we can design Web Services. Our SOAP main role is to store the broadcasted data into our database, and it makes possible to read the measurements by the PHP Web Application so that the users can see them in their Internet Browser.

8.3. PHP WEB APPLICATION

The Web Application is written with an index page of HTML. The backend part is written in PHP. We use the Twig extension to easily map the properties retrieved from the SOAP Service to an HTML page.

The general idea about the application is that we click on one of two buttons:

1. Get Data
2. Get Tweets

The Get Data button will POST to the PHP application that will make a call to the SOAP Service to retrieve the data. When the data is retrieved, it will pass the array as a parameter to the Twig page. The Twig page will then in a for loop create table rows and paste the data into the columns.

The Get Tweet button will POST to the PHP application that will make a call to the Twitter API to fetch the latest 5 Tweets from the user @malldae [Fisherman's Friend]. This is the user we use in the Proxy to Tweet the sensor information. We also call the API to fetch the latest 5 Tweets from @FishinginSweden [Fishing-in-Sweden]. The results are then passed as a nested array to our Twig page. The Twig page will then have the logic to fetch out the correct values from the nested arrays and display this on the page in a formatted manner.

8.4. THE 3RD PARTY WEB SERVICE (TWITTER API)

Twitter's API provides programmatic access to read and write Twitter data. Create a new Tweet, read user profile and follower data, and more (Twitter Developer Documentation, 2016a, 2016b).

In order to use the API, we had to sign up for an account and register our application in its developer page so that we can authenticate our Proxy and PHP Web Application in the code behind each time we use it.

Once we've done that we can have our application tweeting instead of us manually doing the same. Basically we could build any system that can act on behalf of our user with a lot of opportunities: follow accounts, retweet posts, search for hashtags and more.

9. GENERAL TOOLS

The following are tools that we used which are not Scrum related, but secured a streamlined development process.

9.1.1. IDE – VISUAL STUDIO

Visual Studio was our main IDE (*Integrated Development Environment*) for developing everything C# related. It is a software application provided to us free through the Microsoft Imagine program (*previously known as DreamSpark*). It is an IDE that we are all familiar with, so it was an obvious choice. Furthermore, it works seamlessly with Team Services and GIT for project management and source control which are explained in detail previously (*See Section 3.2 Scrum Tools*).

9.1.2. SHARED FOLDERS – ONEDRIVE

We used Microsoft OneDrive as a common platform for files, images and everything related to the report. Every team member has access to our shared folder, which meant that everything was always available to everyone in the cloud and it allowed us to write the report simultaneously.

9.1.3. AZURE CLOUD SERVICES

In this project, we wanted as much of our work and software to be hosted in the cloud (See Appendix 2 and 3). However, before we did that we created a local database in order to test that our Proxy could pick up the broadcasted data and store it in the database. Of course, this has some serious drawbacks as this means that each person working on the project will need a local copy of this and because the data is constantly changing this is not a feasible solution. After having tested that our Proxy behaved as expected we created an SQL Server in Azure where we created our SQL database with the appropriate tables. Now every team member could easily pull the latest source code of the project without having to worry about whether the database was up-to-date or not as this is now always updated and available in the cloud.

Because we wanted to allow multiple web-based applications to access the database regardless of their physical location we created a web service to which the applications can send a SOAP request with the parameters for the search. The Web Service will then use the necessary service method and call the database. In the end the server returns a response in XML format which the application can integrate and use as preferred.

10. CONCLUSION

The aim of our project was to fully comply with the Agile Practices and its selected methodologies like Scrum and Extreme Programming. We defined our Problem Definition deliberately according to this, and questioned a sub-problem too, which refers to the feasibility of them in case of a small team consisting only three members. Our focus was to get a hands-on experience using Scrum. This meant that our final product is very simple and that the idea itself. But because it was simple and unrealistic it allowed us to focus on getting used to Scrum and focus and our project management on not worry too much about getting the perfect idea.

While doing the project, we observed that with a small project like ours, it was not a hindering for us being only three. However, it became clear that if the project was in fact a larger project, then the Product Owner and the Scrum Master would have more tasks and thus not be able to take off their respective hats and put on a developer hat. If we were to do a larger project, we would recommend being more than three so that the Scrum Master and Product Owner can focus entirely on the tasks ahead of them. We recognized what applying the Collective Ownership practice of XP meant to us. We outlined and defined the roles we perform during the three weeks, however the boundaries were not so strict thus we crossed them and forged into one collaboratively acting team.

It was a wonderful and learning experience to work with Agile and Scrum. At the end of Sprint 1 we finally had the “click” and understood the idea of Scrum, which is also why we chose to cancel the sprint a few hours early – to be able to make the preparations for the next - real Scrum - Sprint. Keeping the mindset “*Responding to change over following a plan*” helped us a great deal with the transition from *misunderstood* Scrum to *understanding* Scrum. It made it easier for us to scrap all the preliminary work and re-do it to make it fit our project better than before.

Looking back, having only one User Story, which in reality was an Epic and should have been broken down into several User Stories, made it more difficult to write Acceptance Criteria that covered the entire project. Instead of having Acceptance Criteria that also included reading / displaying the latest sensor information we only had Acceptance Criteria towards the Tweets, as that was indeed all our User Story involved. It would have been easier for us, and the client, to have User Stories that involved the pure sensor data, the Tweets and the application in itself. That way, we would be able to write Acceptance Criteria to fit the entire product that, in fact was expected to be delivered.

This project reveals the nature of a rapid and cost-effective Systems Development and gave us the opportunity to experience and understand many of the topics that are new to us in this semester. Moreover, we are able to compare all the practices with last semester’s main development methodology, the Unified Process. We can clearly state that Agile and its practices perfectly fit to our given time frame of three weeks.

The joy of working and the thrill involved while tackling the various problems means that we can adjudicate that we are glad to have acquired a brand-new methodology. We believe our skills and competences have improved significantly and we would absolutely incorporate the Scrum framework in future projects.

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12. APPENDICES

12.1. APPENDIX 1: DOMAIN MODEL

We came to the conclusion after 15 minutes of diagramming that the domain model would not add any particular value to our product. We already have the idea about the project and don't feel the need to search or explore the project in order to get an idea of where we are heading.

The thing is that after crating the architectural diagram so early in the process we already knew which concepts and domains that is present in the project. Therefor we discarded the continuation of diagramming the domain model.

Appendix 1

12.2. APPENDIX 2: ARCHITECTURE

We used the introduction day of the project to first find the scope and settle on the overall architecture of the solution.

OVERALL ARCHITECTURE

Appendix 2

CORE ARCHITECTURE

Appendix 3

12.3. APPENDIX 4: SCRUM MEETING DIARY

Sprint zero						
PP, CM ₁						
Sprint 1						
S ₁		S ₂		S ₃ + SR + SP + CM ₂		
Sprint 2						
S ₄		S ₅		S ₆ + SR + SP + CM ₃		
Sprint 3						
S ₇		S ₈		S ₉ + SR + CM ₄		
Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday

Appendix 4

Legend:

- S1 – S9: Scrum Meetings
- SR: Sprint Retrospective
- SP: Sprint Planning
- CM: Client Meeting
- PP: Project Proposal

12.4. APPENDIX 5: TWITTER FEED

Fisherman's Friend
@malldae
Joined September 2016

TWEETS 55 FOLLOWING 13 MOMENTS 0

Tweets Tweets & replies

Fisherman's Friend @malldae · Dec 5
Wind 49 km/h. Strong breeze. Moderate storm is expected! Fishing with care!
Temperature is 30 Celcius
#lambdaweather2016

Fisherman's Friend @malldae · Dec 5
Wind speed is 216 km/h. Very severe cyclonic storm is expected. Stay safe!
#lambdaweather2016

Fisherman's Friend @malldae · Dec 5
Wind speed is 71 km/h. Cyclonic storm is expected. Stay ashore!
#lambdaweather2016

Fisherman's Friend @malldae · Dec 5
Wind speed is 214 km/h. Very severe cyclonic storm is expected. Stay

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- Mogens Camre
- #fintech
18.2K Tweets
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- Politiken

Appendix 5

12.5. APPENDIX 6: SECTIONS & RESPONSIBILITY

Which Section?		Who?
Introduction		Casper, Toke, Istvan
Problem Definition		Istvan
Comply with Agile Practices	<i>Extreme Programming</i>	Istvan
	<i>Scrum Tools</i>	Casper
	<i>Team Services</i>	Casper
Sprint Zero	<i>Project Proposal</i>	Istvan
	<i>Definition of Done</i>	Toke
	<i>Testing</i>	Casper
	<i>Writing User Stories</i>	Istvan
	<i>Overall Planning</i>	Casper, Toke
	<i>Sprint 1 Planning</i>	Casper
	<i>Planning Poker</i>	Toke
Sprint 1	<i>Sprint Backlog</i>	Casper
	<i>Scrum Meeting</i>	Istvan
	<i>Burndown chart</i>	Casper
	<i>Done</i>	Casper
	<i>Sprint Retrospective</i>	Casper, Toke, Istvan
	<i>Sprint Review</i>	Istvan
	<i>Sprint 2 Planning</i>	Casper
Sprint 2	<i>Sprint Backlog</i>	Istvan
	<i>Scrum Meeting</i>	Istvan
	<i>Burndown chart</i>	Istvan
	<i>Done</i>	Casper, Toke
	<i>Sprint Retrospective</i>	Istvan
	<i>Sprint Review</i>	Casper, Toke, Istvan
	<i>Sprint 3 Planning</i>	Casper
Sprint 3	<i>Sprint Backlog</i>	Toke
	<i>Scrum Meeting</i>	Istvan

	<i>Burndown chart</i>	Toke
	<i>Done</i>	Toke
	<i>Sprint Retrospective</i>	Casper, Toke, Istvan
	<i>Sprint Review</i>	Casper, Toke, Istvan
	<i>Acceptance Test</i>	Toke
Technical Documentation	<i>UDP Sensor Broadcaster</i>	Istvan
	<i>Proxy/UDP receiver</i>	Toke
	<i>SOAP Service</i>	Istvan
	<i>PHP Web Application</i>	Casper
	<i>3rd party Web Service</i>	Istvan
General Tools		Toke
Conslusion		Casper, Toke, Istvan